

Indigoid Vat Dyes of the Isatin Series. Indole-thionaphtheneindigos.

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In view of the observation made by one of us (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 680) that the scarlet-red shades obtained from 2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigo and its halogen-derivatives on cotton as well as on wool are deeper than those obtained from Ciba scarlet-G and its halogen derivatives (Guha, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 423), it appeared of interest to make a systematic study of similar vat dyes in the isatin series as 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo (Bezdzik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908, -9, 376 ; E. P. 17162/06) and its dibromo derivative (E. P. 6490/07) have received technical application under the name of Thioindigo scarlet-R and Ciba red-G respectively.

With this object in view, isatin and its various derivatives were condensed with 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 541) and the following compounds prepared: 3-indole-, 3-(5-chloro)-indole-, 3-(5-bromo)-indole-, 3-(5-iodo)-indole-, 3-(5:7-dibromo)-indole-, 3-(5-bromo-7-nitro)-indole-, 3-(5:7-dinitro)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo. It was noticed in every case that condensation proceeded with the greatest ease and the products separated rapidly in well-defined crystalline form. They are all soluble in pyridine with magenta red colour, soluble in aniline and nitrobenzene; except the first named compound, which is moderately soluble in alcohol, the rest are very sparingly soluble in the same solvent. When heated above 310°, these dyes melt and quickly volatilise evolving coloured vapours of the respective substances which deposit again as pure dyes (*cf.* Guha, *loc. cit.*).

These indigoid dyes dye wool evenly from an acid bath when freshly precipitated by water from the concentrated sulphuric acid solution in which they dissolve producing characteristic coloration. All of them, excepting the dinitro compound which forms a yellow vat, yield light yellow vat by means of alkaline hydrosulphite and

from it the dye is reprecipitated when exposed to air. The compounds described, are arranged above according to the gradual increase of the depth of the shades of the dyes obtained on wool as well as on cotton. Of the scarlet-red shades obtained from the first four substances, the one that is obtained from the iodo compound is the deepest. The dibromo derivative produces a deep red shade. The bromonitro and the dinitro compounds give rise to dark red shades and the shade obtained from the latter is the deeper of the two. It has also been found that the scarlet red shades obtained from the indigoid dyes derived from isatin, its 5-chloro and 5-bromo derivatives are distinctly deeper than those obtained from the nearly corresponding dyes in the acenaphthenequinone series (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

Finally, for the purpose of comparison of dyeing shades on wool and on cotton, the analogously composed 2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthreneindigo was prepared. This substance is dark chocolate, it dyes wool in brown shades from an acid bath and dyes cotton in dull brown colour from a yellow alkaline hydrosulphite vat.

It has been assumed that the β -ketonic group in isatin and its various derivatives takes part in the reaction from the analogy of the constitution of the similar compound, 3-indole-2-thionaphtheneindigo and its dibromo derivative (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

5:7-Dinitroisatin.—In preparing this substance we have employed the following modification of Menon, Perkin and Robinsons' method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 840) which also gave pure and almost quantitative yield. To a solution of powdered isatin (2.5 g.) in strong sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 25 c.c.) cooled to 0°, finely powdered potassium nitrate (25 g.) was added in small quantities at a time, keeping the temperature within 15° and the mixture stirred thoroughly. The resulting thick brownish-yellow mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and then heated on a water-bath at 50-55° with continuous stirring. After one hour canary yellow precipitate began to separate, the heating was continued for 2 hours more when the separation was almost complete; the mixture poured into crushed ice with stirring and allowed to stand overnight in a cooled chamber and filtered; the residue on the filter paper was washed well with

ice-cold water and dried. It was finally crystallised from xylene in prisms, m. p. 209-10° yield 2.3 g.

It is readily soluble in pyridine, acetone, ethyl acetate; soluble in acetic acid, alcohol, amyl alcohol, xylene and in hot water; sparingly soluble in chloroform, benzene and ether; insoluble in ligroin and carbon tetrachloride.

3-Indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-thionaphtheneindigo.

Isatin (0.294 g.), dissolved in boiling glacial acetic acid, was mixed with 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in hot acetic acid (10 c.c.). The resulting red-brown solution, on treatment with a small quantity of strong hydrochloric acid and shaking turned dark red (almost black) and silky scarlet red beautiful needles separated. The mixture was boiled for 15-20 minutes to complete the reaction, filtered while still hot, washed with acetic acid and with hot water. It was purified by heating with 50% acetic acid and finally crystallised from acetic acid in fibre-like silky scarlet red needles. The substance is soluble in chloroform, acetone, acetic acid, toluene and less so in benzene; sparingly soluble in carbon tetrachloride and ligroin. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it with olive brown coloration. It dyes wool in brilliant and pleasant scarlet red shade from an acid bath and dyes cotton in light red shade from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat at 50-60°. Attempts to dye cotton from cold hydrosulphite vat in order to obtain the desired deep scarlet red shade were not, however, met with success (cf. 3-indole-2'-thionaphtheneindigo, Rowe, *Colour Index* No. 1225, 1924 edition). (Found: S, 11.19. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2NS$ requires S, 10.92 per cent).

The indole-thionaphtheneindigos described in Table I were prepared in a similar way. They were purified by boiling with alcohol and finally crystallised from pyridine, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, hot water and dried at 150°.

Table I.
 T = Thionaphtheneindigo, $m = 5$ -methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene.

Name.	Mol. Formula.	Method of preparation.	Appearance.	Solubilities.	Colour in strong H_2SO_4 .	Shade on wool from acid bath.	Shade on cotton from hydro-sulphite vat.	Analysis Found.	Calc.
(1) 3-(5-Chloro)-indole-2'-(5-methyl)-T	$C_{17}H_{10}O_2NCIS$	5-Chloroisatin + m	Silky scarlet-red small needles	Difficultly soluble in amyl alcohol, xylene, acetic acid; sparingly soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone	Olive green	Scarlet red.	Scarlet red.	Cl, 10.63	10.83
(2) 3-(5-Bromo)-indole-2'-(5-methyl)-T	$C_{17}H_{10}O_2NBrS$	5-Bromoisatin + m	Silky scarlet-red fibre-like needles	Do	Do	Do	Do	Br, 21.85	21.51
(3) 3-(5-Iodo)-indole-2'-(5-methyl)-T	$C_{17}H_{10}O_2NIS$	5-Iodoisatin + m	Deep scarlet-red silky needles	Do	Do	Deep scarlet red	Deep scarlet red	I, 30.24	30.31
(4) 3-(5:7-Dibromo)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-T	$C_{17}H_9O_2NBr_2S$	5:7-Dibromoisatin + m	Deep red fibre-like clusters of silky needles	Sparingly soluble in amyl alcohol, acetic acid, benzene, xylene	Do	Deep red	Deep red	Br, 35.82	35.47
(5) 3-(5-Bromo-7-nitro)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-T	$C_{17}H_9O_4N_2BrS$	5-Bromo-7-nitroisatin + m	Dark red small needles	Sparingly soluble in chloroform, amyl alcohol, benzene, acetic acid, acetone	Deep green	Dark red	Dark red	Br, 19.58	19.18
(6) 3-(5:7-Dinitro)-indole-2'-(5'-methyl)-T	$C_{17}H_9O_6N_3S$	5:7-Dinitroisatin + m	Dark red glistering needles	Sol. in xylene; diffcultly sol. in acetic acid, acetone, chloroform and benzene	Deep green	Dark red	Do	S, 7.97	8.35

* 2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthreneindigo.

The dye is soluble in amyl alcohol, xylene, pyridine, aniline and nitrobenzene; moderately in chloroform, acetic acid and benzene; sparingly soluble in acetone, and alcohol; strong sulphuric acid dissolves it with reddish-brown coloration. (Found: S, 8.86. $C_{23}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 9.04 per cent).

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* The compound was prepared by methods already described from phenanthraquinone (0.416 g.), methyl hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in glacial acetic acid solution with traces of hydrochloric acid and purified as usual, m.p. 300°.

